

INSTRUCTIONAL INFORMATION

The following module template has been developed as part of Work Package 7 of the EU-funded GoGreen project. The module is designed in a skeletal format to allow for broad adaptation to a wide range of existing curricula and professional development schemes. To enhance flexibility, the module is divided into theme blocks with suggested content, assessments, and activities. The template has been constructed to serve as foundational material for curriculum development or course integration.

INTENDED AUDIENCE

This module may be adapted for the instruction of conservation, conservation science, and the broader cultural heritage sector at the undergraduate, postgraduate, and professional level. The activities and assessments of this module have been developed for both groups and individuals.

MODULE DELIVERY

Content in this module supports in-person, hybrid, or through virtual learning. The following online resources may be used for hybrid or virtual module instruction.

1. <https://padlet.com/>
2. <https://whiteboard.microsoft.com>
3. <https://www.mural.co/>

PRE-REQUISITE KNOWLEDGE

This module has no suggested learning pre-requisites to enable broader application of module contents to diverse audiences. Module-takers should have a general familiarity with sustainability and cultural heritage, and an openness to learning about how conservation and heritage care can support sustainable development.

MISSION STATEMENT

To promote leadership in green conservation by empowering students and professionals to become advocates for green conservation practices, equipped with the knowledge, tools and skills needed to inspire adaptable, community-driven strategies for the long-term stewardship of cultural heritage.

DESCRIPTION

Leadership in Green Conservation equips learners to champion sustainability in conservation by developing leadership skills to promote green(er) practices. The module integrates theoretical perspectives with practical approaches for green(er) solutions, exploring their relevance in both institutional and professional contexts. It serves not only the conservation sector but also the wider cultural heritage field, engaging relevant stakeholders and affiliated professionals. Additionally, the topics proposed in the module promote interdisciplinary engagement and collaboration, positioning these as essential components of sustainable practice.

A central focus of the module is to encourage learners to develop a personal voice in advocating for green(er) conservation and heritage care practices. Through activities, learners design and implement a personalised green action project, applying key concepts to real-world projects. The assessment suggestions provided allow them to keep track of their progress and check their level of understanding. These projects evolve throughout the module, shaped by new insights and resources, fostering a dynamic and interactive learning experience. Learners are also encouraged to reflect on the challenges of their projects and consider their future potential.

LEARNING GOALS AND OUTCOMES

Main Goal Equip students and professionals with the comprehensive knowledge of the latest sustainable development policies, legislations, tools, skills and methodologies within the cultural heritage sector, to enable them to become a leading voice in addressing the risks and challenges of the climate emergency on heritage care.

Subsidiary Goals

- Develop an understanding of how sustainability is debated and defined within the theory and practice of cultural heritage care.
- Cultivate awareness of the importance of reflecting on one's practice and developing reflection skills for lifelong learning of green conservation practices in cultural heritage care.
- Develop leadership and communication competences to advocate for green conservation practices for the care of cultural heritage.
- Encourage interdisciplinary collaboration to deepen understanding of and foster responses to sustainability challenges within one's sphere of influence.

By the end of this module,

Learning Outcomes

- 1) **(Analysis)** Analyse the reciprocal relationship between cultural heritage and sustainability.
- 2) **(Application)** Evaluate and synthesise a wide range of data sources and materials in various formats to develop and implement green conservation strategies.
- 3) **(Assessment)** Gain an overview of existing policies, standards, guidelines, and methodologies adopted in the cultural heritage sector that address sustainability to identify existing gaps and emerging challenges.
- 4) **(Reflection)** Reflect on personal practice by assessing one's own professional or academic work through the lens of the green conservation definition and parameters.
- 5) **(Advocacy)** Promote and advocate green(er) conservation strategies within one's sphere of influence using communication tools.

RECOMMEND READINGS

Visit the GoGreen Zenodo for the full module bibliography.

Fife, G., Turrina, A., Wagner, J., Del Curto, D., Southwick, C., Keune, K. (TBD). 'Defining Green in the Conservation of Cultural Heritage' to be submitted (for Studies in Conservation)

ICOMOS Climate Change and Cultural Heritage Working Group. (2019). *The Future of Our Pasts: Engaging Cultural Heritage in Climate Action*. ICOMOS. <https://civviih.icomos.org/wp-content/uploads/Future-of-Our-Pasts-Report-min.pdf>

ICOMOS Sustainable Development Goals Working Group, Labadi, S., Giliberto, F., Rosetti, I., Shetabi, L., & Yildirim, E. (2021). *Heritage and the sustainable development goals: Policy guidance for heritage and development actors*. ICOMOS.

Tate-Harte, A., & Thickett, D. (2024). Calculating the Carbon Footprint of Interventive and Preventive Conservation at English Heritage, UK. *Studies in Conservation*, 69(sup1), 323–332. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00393630.2024.2336814>

Taylor, J., & Boersma, F. (2018). Managing Environments for Collections: The Impact of International Loans on Sustainable Climate Strategies. *Studies in Conservation*, 63(sup1), 257–261. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00393630.2018.1504514>

United Nations. (2023). *Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals (GHS Rev. 10, 2023)* (10th ed). United Nations Economic Commission for Europe. <https://unece.org/transport/dangerous-goods/ghs-rev10-2023>

European Commission. Joint Research Centre. (2024). Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials: Methodological guidance. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/28450>

GoGreen Work Package 8 (2024). *GoGreen Webinar—Defining Green Conservation* [Video recording]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?si=YnV86t7f45-PCOHC&v=xR0eA8nGsMw&feature=youtu.be>

LEADERSHIP IN GREEN CONSERVATION				
THEME	TOPICS	DESCRIPTION	LEARNING OUTCOMES	SUGGESTED ACTIVITIES AND ASSESSMENTS
The Role of Cultural Heritage for Sustainable Development	<i>Sustainability and Cultural Heritage</i>	Introduces general policies, frameworks, and guidelines for sustainable development and how they may be relevant to cultural heritage.	Analyse the reciprocal relationship between cultural heritage and sustainability.	<p>Activity: Link the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to cultural heritage practice highlighting ways in which practice aligns with the goals and possible future adaptations.</p> <p>Assessment Action Project: Individually or in a group, design and develop an action project throughout the module that identifies ways to promote sustainable development within your personal sphere of influence. Projects should connect module concepts to real-world contexts and highlight opportunities for green(er) practice and impact within conservation and cultural heritage care</p>
	<i>Cultural Heritage Care, Resources, and the Environment</i>	Through suggested case studies, topic explores the reciprocal relationship between cultural heritage, resources, and the environment.		
	<i>Human Health and Well-Being, and Societal Impact Areas</i>	Explores the positive and negative impacts of cultural heritage on the remaining two impact areas (human health and well-being, and societal impact). Aids learners in establishing a personal vision for sustainable development in cultural heritage through drafting a personal action project .		
Frameworks for Sustainable Development in Cultural Heritage Care	<i>Sustainability in Cultural Heritage Care Policies, Standards, and Guidelines</i>	Highlights cultural heritage specific policies, standards, and guidelines that address sustainable development.	Gain an overview of existing policies, standards, guidelines, and methodologies adopted in the cultural heritage sector that address sustainability to identify existing gaps and emerging challenges.	<p>Activity: Investigate a policy, standard, or guideline specific to the sustainable development of conservation and cultural heritage care. Identify impact areas addressed and any limitations.</p>
Green Thinking: What is Green Conservation?	<i>Exploring the Green Definition, Parameters, and Frameworks</i>	Introduces the definition of green conservation and the parameters and frameworks used to make green(er) decisions. Learners will explore how green thinking drives conservation and cultural heritage care decision-making.		<p>Activity: Engage in a group roleplay or reflect independently, consider the application of the green definition and frameworks in conservation and cultural heritage care practice.</p> <p>Assessment Action Project Cont'd: Continue building on the action project. Consider the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Why were some green parameters not included, and what trade-offs were considered? How might these excluded parameters affect the overall impact of the project, if at all?
Green Tools and Resources for Cultural Heritage Care	<i>Strategies and Tools for Green Conservation Practices</i>	Explores strategies and tools employed within the cultural heritage sector to address the 4 impact areas on sustainable development.	Evaluate and synthesise a wide range of data sources and materials in various formats to develop and implement green conservation strategies.	<p>Assessment: Select a conservation material, method, or practice and assess its sustainability across the four impact areas: natural environment and climate, resources and materials, human health and well-being, and cultural heritage. Then apply a green conservation tool or framework (e.g., STiCH, GHS, GCC, etc.) to evaluate the practice, considering how the tool or framework assesses it and what greener strategies may be adopted.</p> <p>Activity: Practice applying the Decision-Making Model on a personal case study.</p>
	<i>Interdisciplinary Considerations for Green Conservation Practices</i>	Examines methods and perspectives from multiple disciplines to inform green decision-making in conservation and cultural heritage care.		<p>Assessment: Investigate strategies and practices from other disciplines and geographical locations that could be adapted to promote sustainable development in your conservation or cultural heritage care context. Consider potential challenges and the future impact of these adaptations on conservation and cultural heritage care practice.</p>

LEADERSHIP IN GREEN CONSERVATION				
THEME	TOPICS	DESCRIPTION	LEARNING OUTCOMES	ACTIVITIES + ASSESSMENTS
Green Advocacy: Skill-Training, Future Proofing, Accessibility, and Social Cohesion	<i>Role of Advocacy in Cultural Heritage Care</i>	Encourages learners to consider integrating green(er) practices in their personal contexts by introducing them to communication strategies, and the role of outreach in advocating for green conservation practice. Module-takers will learn how to best use their sphere of influence for change.	Promote and advocate green(er) conservation strategies within one’s sphere of influence using communication tools.	<p>Group Activity: Engage in a one-on-one peer roleplay exercise advocating for green(er) approaches to conservation. Take turns playing the devil’s advocate!</p> <p>Activity: Map your sphere of influence to consider approaches when advocating for green(er) strategies</p> <p>Activity: Reflect on policies in professional practice and highlight areas which can incorporate green(er) strategies for cultural heritage care.</p>
	<i>Green Leadership in Action: Personal Projects</i>	Provides learners with the opportunity to present and reflect on their personal green leadership action projects. Projects should consider long-term impact towards green(er) approaches in conservation and cultural heritage care.	Reflect on personal practice by assessing one’s own professional or academic work through the lens of the green conservation definition and parameters.	<p>Action Project: Report and present on the action project developed during the module. How can you incorporate the things you have learned to improve the impact of your project?</p>

DISCLAIMER

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

AUTHORS AND CONTRIBUTORS

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